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Acronyms

Acronym	Description
AR	Augmented Reality
AT	Assistive Technologies
BSC	Barcelona Supercomputing Center
ENG	Engineering
EU	European Union
ISO	International Organisation for Standardisation
IT	Information Technology
UAB	Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona
UI	User Interface
UD	Universal Design
WP	Work Package
WCAG	Web Content Accessibility Guidelines

Executive Summary

This deliverable reports on the usability and accessibility of the GreenSCENT platform and related applications (apps) and educational resources. This includes the interface, along with the digital tools and activities (demonstrators), and educational material, developed throughout the project.

In keeping with the principles of Universal Design (UD), the usability of the platform and apps developed were tested against two international accessibility standards: the [Web Content Accessibility Guidelines](#) (WCAG 2.2) and the EU standard [EN301 549](#). When UD principles were not met, accessibility measures were subsequently taken. This deliverable is divided into four main sections. The first introductory section provides definitions for the key terms used throughout. With key terms established, the second section of this deliverable outlines the guiding principle that guides this project, namely, “leaving no one behind.” Guided by this principle, the following sections detail the steps taken to ensure the accessibility and usability of the technological tools, activities and materials developed throughout the project. These include:

- GreenSCENT website developed by Uninettuno
- GreenSCENT platform developed by Engineering (ENG)
- Four technological tools:
 - Immersive interactive storytelling platform (GreenVerse) developed by ENG
 - Augmented reality (AR) app on air quality developed by Barcelona Supercomputing Center (BSC)
 - Citizen journalism app developed by ENG
 - Air quality app and platform for CleanAir@Schools developed by 4sfera
- Farm to Fork innovation challenge platform developed by Agorize
- Teacher training kits developed by Uninettuno.

UAB oversees this deliverable with contributions from ENG, BSC, 4sfera, Agorize, Uninettuno and Democracy X (formally the Danish Board of Technology).

Introduction: Definition of terms

The purpose of this deliverable is to ensure that all the tools (demonstrators), information, media assets and resources have a single point of entry in the GreenSCENT platform. This platform will provide users with easy access to all the project's tools, demonstrators, information, media and resources. The platform itself is designed to be multilingual and accessible in multiple formats, catering to diverse users with different access needs, facilitated by translation engines developed by our technical partner Pangeanic.

Drawing on the ISO/IEC Guide 71:2014, *Guide for addressing accessibility in standards*, we mark a distinction between the terms “accessibility” and “usability”. “Usability” refers to the combination of the “effectiveness, efficiency and satisfaction with which specified users achieve specified goals in particular environments” (ISO 9241 standard, 2013). Tied to usability is the concept of UD, which refers to the design of products, environments, programmes and services that are usable by everyone, to the greatest extent

possible, without the need for adaptation or specialised design. UD does not exclude assistive devices for particular groups or persons with disabilities where necessary.

In contrast, “accessibility” describes the extent to which a product or service can be used by a diverse range of people to achieve a specified goal in a specific context ([ISO 26800](#)). “Assistive products” refer to the extent to which a product can be used by specified users to achieve specific goals with effectiveness, efficiency and satisfaction in a specified context of use (ISO 9241-11: 1998, 3.1). However, we acknowledge that some standards define accessibility as “usability of a product, service, environment or facility by individuals with the widest range of capabilities” (ISO 9241-171; ISO/IEC 25062; and ISO/IEC 29136). This perspective emphasises that accessibility involves both ease of use (which can affect task efficiency and user satisfaction) and success of use (i.e. system effectiveness). Within the literature, a variety of terms are used interchangeably to refer to design approaches that prioritise usability for a broad range of users. These terms include UD, Accessible Design, Design for All, Barrier-Free Design, Inclusive Design and Transgenerational Design. While there are subtle nuances in emphasis, all terms share the core objective to create products, environments, and services that are usable by the widest possible population, regardless of age, ability, or circumstances. For the purposes of the GreenSCENT project, we followed the EU standard EN301542 on digital accessibility, ensuring that we applied UD principles at the beginning of the design stage of every Information Technology (IT) service or product we developed. We also followed UD principles in the design of the project’s visual identity, as discussed later in Section 2.

1. Inclusive approach: Leaving no one behind

The GreenSCENT project is designed to cater to all, irrespective of age, sex, disability, ethnicity, origin, religion, economic or social status. Building on the UN principle of *leaving no one behind*, we recognise the importance of developing accessible technical solutions that safeguard against exclusion. For this reason, we chose to follow the principles of UD, whenever possible, rather than opting for assistive technologies. While it is difficult to ensure the accessibility of any product or service for all users, prioritising user needs from the design stage and conducting usability tests throughout development can significantly improve accessibility for a wider audience. This aligns with the recommendation outlined in the European Standard EN 301549.

1.2 Internal accessibility awareness amongst GreenSCENT partners

To promote internal awareness of accessibility within the GreenSCENT project, all partners participated in several training sessions during the monthly communication and dissemination (WP6) meetings. These sessions focused on how to create accessible online content. This focus on internal media accessibility was considered the first step towards achieving consistent accessibility across all GreenSCENT communication and dissemination materials. The following accessibility recommendations were included (see D6.2. for more details):

- **Use camel case hashtags in social media content:** Camel case hashtags make it easier for users, including those who use screen readers, to understand and navigate online content.

- **Incorporate alternative text for images:** Alternative text (Alt Txt) provides a textual description of images, which allows individuals who use screen readers to understand the visual content.
- **Include emojis at the end of sentences in social media posts:** The use of emojis in social media posts can enhance the overall meaning and emotional tone of a message, particularly for individuals who may have difficulty interpreting written language. However, if emojis are used excessively or placed in the middle of sentences, it may create difficulty for users who use screen readers.
- **Check the accessibility of your content:** Ensuring that content can be read by screen readers ensures accessibility for individuals who are blind or partially blind. We advised partners to always check the accessibility of their online content using the [Screen Reader Chrome extension](#).
- **Check the colour contrast:** We advised partners to use the [Contrast Checker tool](#) to ensure that the images they use have adequate contrast, which can make it easier for individuals with visual impairments to perceive visual content.
- **Create accessible videos:** We encouraged partners to create accessible videos to ensure that their audiovisual material can be understood by individuals with a range of abilities, including those who are Deaf or hard of hearing, who may rely on closed captioning.
- **Accessible events:** For all events, we advised partners to take steps to ensure that their event is inclusive and usable by individuals with a range of abilities, such as providing live captioning or sign language interpreters. We applied these principles to the organisation of three conferences of the Green Digital Accessibility conference in 2022-2024. Measures included the provision of captioning services and accessible PowerPoint templates for presenters.

As part of this work, we created a user-friendly media toolkit to break down barriers and encourage broader participation in climate activism, which is available at the following link: <https://zenodo.org/records/12607947>.

2. GreenSCENT webpage

2.1 Usability tests

The GreenSCENT website was created in M1 by Uninettuno. In M3, the website specifications were defined in D6.1. This head start allowed GreenSCENT communication to begin posting news and information from the beginning of the project. However, decisions related to the project visual identity were required. This update formed part of WP6 but is included here because they involve accessibility.

Regarding the visual identity, all colours and images used in the dissemination of the project and design of the front end of the GreenSCENT platform, website and all apps were required to be accessible.

As part of the GreenSCENT project, we took a comprehensive approach to ensure that the website was fully accessible and usable for all users, including those with disabilities. Our accessibility guidelines were designed to adhere to the latest industry standards, specifically the Web Content Accessibility Guidelines (WCAG) 2.1 level AA.

The first measure we took was to ensure compliance with these guidelines, which included proper use of headings to provide a clear structure for the content on the website. This helped users with cognitive or visual impairments navigate the website more easily, as headings can provide a way for screen readers to understand the content hierarchy and for users to orient themselves on the page.

The second measure was to simplify the navigation of the website, which involved creating a clear and intuitive navigation menu, using properly labelled links and buttons, and organising the content logically. This helped users with cognitive or motor impairments navigate the website more easily, as well as improve the overall usability of the website for all users.

We added Alt Txt for images, so that users with visual impairments could understand the meaning of images. We also ensured that all functionality on the website could be accessed using only a keyboard, which helped users with motor impairments navigate the website more easily.

Furthermore, we made sure to have a sufficient colour contrast between text and background to make it easy to read for users with low vision. We also provided alternative accessible versions of non-text content such as videos, so users with visual or auditory impairments could still understand the content. Lastly, we used user-friendly language and avoided using jargon or complex terms to make the website accessible to all users, including those who may not have specific subject knowledge.

Regular testing and monitoring of the website was also a key step in our accessibility guidelines. These guidelines were reviewed and updated regularly as technology changed and new accessibility best practices emerged.

3. GreenSCENT Platform

3.1 Front end: look and feel

To access the GreenSCENT web platform, users can simply visit the website's URL at greenvrse.net. Once on the home page (as shown in Figure 1), users will find a top ribbon that displays the project logo and a set of clickable icons. These icons provide access to a range of useful functions, such as enabling or disabling accessibility options, changing the interface language, and editing user profiles.

The central area of the home page consists of five sections, each catering to specific user needs. The **"CREATE"** section allows registered users to access a repository of videos and images (2D and 360°) that can be used as a background for creating new immersive and interactive content (image and video). The **"LIBRARY"** section offers registered users access to a repository of immersive and interactive content (images and videos) produced by the user community to which the individual belongs. The **"ALL MEDIA"** section provides registered users with a library of multimedia resources of all types generated by the user community to which the individual belongs. These multimedia resources can be shared via URL or QR Code, and they can also be used as annotation elements to create new immersive and interactive content. Additionally, the **"CITIZEN JOURNALISM"** section provides registered users access to a list of all environmental reports, along with comprehensive information for each report, such as its status, a detailed description, and geographical coordinates to locate the environmental issue. In this section, registered users can also create new environmental reports. Lastly, the **"EXPLORE"** section grants access to a public archive area that is open to both registered and unregistered users. This section contains all the content that has been made public by the platform's users, providing users with additional information and content to explore. The home page also includes a lower ribbon that displays the logos of consortium partners and provides information about the funding received from the European Commission.

Figure 1. GreenSCENT platform home page.

The GreenSCENT platform's design incorporates colours that represent the green economy and sustainability.

To achieve a sense of unity and balance, the design employs an analogous colour scheme. These colours share similar undertones, allowing them to seamlessly transition and create a cohesive visual identity. The colour palette is composed of the five colours that are included in the original logo of the project (see Figure 2).

Figure 2. Colour palette with their hex representation.

The coolest colour (used in the lower ribbon) is #00364b, a blue very close to Prussian Blue (DeltaE=6.95, 93% similar). The second coolest is a dark green #004B49. This colour is called Deep Jungle Green. The mild green in the centre of the logo is the dominant hue of the interface. The colour is #01796f (Pine Green). The light green #43A459C is named Blue Green (Munsell). The final warm colour is a yellow orange named Xanthous, #F1B42F. Variations of the palette can be found in some graphic elements of the interface.

With a clean layout and intuitive interface, the GreenSCENT platform is easy to navigate. The imagery used reinforces the project's core values of environmentalism, solidarity, inclusivity, and sustainability (see Figure 3). The colours are based on the palette already described, with some minor variations.

Figure 3. A sample of the images used in the GreenSCENT website interface.

The font chosen for the GreenSCENT platform is Roboto, which is a modern sans-serif typeface used as the default font for its Android operating system. It was first introduced in 2011 and has since gained widespread popularity due to its clarity and readability across various screen sizes and resolutions. Its well-balanced letterforms and generous spacing make it legible, even in small text sizes, which is essential for user interfaces and digital content. Moreover, Roboto is optimised for screen readability. Its open letterforms, ample spacing, and clear distinction between characters ensure optimal legibility on various devices, enhancing the user experience across different screen resolutions.

3.1.1 Usability tests

ENG performed internal test sessions to improve usability and accessibility of the platform. The platform underwent rigorous testing, including both internal unit and integration testing by developers, and comprehensive testing by independent professionals. These testers reviewed all features, starting with the requirements' analysis. They followed a well-defined process that included test planning based on specifications, test design, and execution. The final report identified bugs and led to improvements in the quality of the software. Insights and findings from each test session informed the ongoing development of the platform. ENG also conducted regular test sessions throughout the development lifecycle to validate changes, address issues, and ensure the ongoing quality and usability of the platform. All issues and bugs were input into the project management software JIRA that was used to keep track of the requirements, bugs and the software lifecycle management. Specific usability test sessions were also carried out by partners (UAB, Uninettuno), which are described in detail in Section 4.1. Such tests were mainly focused on the Immersive Storytelling tool, but they also offered more general feedback on the platform.

3.1.2 Accessibility measures

The GreenSCENT mobile apps and platform interface are designed to be accessible, adhering to WCAG2.1 and the European EN 301 549 accessibility standards. Additionally, they support multiple European languages, ensuring inclusivity for a diverse range of users.

The web platform allows for language management. To access this feature, users can click on the "languages" icon, as depicted in Figure 4. This opens a dialogue menu that displays a list of languages. After users select their preferred language, the web interface will appear in their chosen language.

Figure 4. Languages list supported in the GreenVerse platform.

Currently, the platform supports five languages: Italian, Catalan, Spanish, Greek, and English with the possibility of adding new ones in the future. Once the initial selection has been made, the web browser remembers the users' choice with the possibility of amending a user's selection at any time.

The web platform offers a range of accessibility features to enhance user experience. To access these features, users can click on the "accessibility" icon . This will open a dialogue page presenting the accessibility options managed by the application, as shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5. Accessibility features of GreenVerse platform.

The accessibility options include the following:

- **Customisable font size:** Users can select from regular, large, X-large, and XX-large font sizes.
- **Dyslexia-friendly font options:** We offer fonts specifically designed to improve readability for individuals with dyslexia.
- **Adjustable colour contrast settings:** Users can modify contrast levels for enhanced legibility.
- **Highlighted links:** Links are clearly indicated with a yellow background for better visibility.
- **Underlined links:** Links are underlined to improve visual recognition.

By making use of these accessibility features, users can create a more tailored and enjoyable browsing experience.

3.1.3 Translation engine integration

The GreenSCENT project uses translation engines supplied by Pangeanic. In October 2022, Pangeanic set up a web-application to allow GreenSCENT users to translate documents into and out of English and the following partners' languages: Italian, Danish, Spanish, Catalan, Serbian, Finnish, and Romanian. UAB is the administrator of the Pangeanic translation engine. Tests on the Pangeanic translation engines were carried out throughout the lifetime of the project to assess the quality of the translation. Following the Bilingual Evaluation Understudy (BLEU) metric and the more recent Metric for Evaluation of Translation with Explicit ORdering (METEOR), quality was assessed by comparing the machine translated subtitles in each language with those created by a human, the results of which formed part of a presentation at the TERMOS conference in Wrocław in 11-13 May 2023.

4. GreenVERSE immersive storytelling platform

4.1 Usability tests

The immersive storytelling platform GreenVerse underwent usability and accessibility testing in Spain (M6 and M18) as part of the ITACA Summer School at UAB and in Italy (M7). A total of 63 participants evaluated the platform's usability. The following sections provide details of these testing activities and results.

4.1.1 ITACA Summer School at UAB 2022 and 2023

The ITACA Summer School is an annual summer school aimed at students in Catalonia, Spain. The purpose of the workshop in ITACA was to test the GreenVerse Immersive Platform for usability and accessibility with students, aged between 15–16 years of age.

Students tested the GreenVerse Immersive Storytelling Platform, providing feedback through discussions and observations. UAB compiled this feedback into an [Excel spreadsheet](#) and categorised issues as 'stories' or 'bugs' in the JIRA management software.

On July 28, 2022, UAB and ENG met to define the first set of issues to be resolved. Together, we identified nine issues to be resolved, by the 30th of September 2022. These issues primarily involved minor platform bugs, such as fixing the full screen preview function and story export functions.

A second meeting on September 28 identified six additional issues, requiring resolution: sharing function, audio problems, save window, font type, and photo upload difficulties.

In February 2023, UAB and ENG met again to address outstanding GreenVerse platform issues. ENG successfully resolved problems related to audio, saving, font adjustments, and photo uploading and editing.

UAB also assisted ENG in the redesign of the GreenVerse homepage, introducing the following structure:

- A "Create" folder for storing 2D or 360 images and videos to build immersive stories.
- A "Library" folder to house users' interactive stories in both completed and draft forms, allowing for editing by the owner and potential collaborators.
- An "Explore" folder to showcase finished interactive stories accessible online without account login, to house the completed interactive stories. This will make it easier for users to share their stories online or on social media.
- A new "Citizen Journalism" folder that enables mobile uploads to the platform.
- An "All Media" folder, which acts as the central repository for all generated media content.

ENG also enhanced the platform by adding a left-hand side menu to the "Create" folder for improved organisation. This menu helps categorise content (icons, 2D images, 360 images, audio etc). Additionally, the platform's domain name was updated to GreenVRerse.

4.1.2 UNINETTUNO description of user testing

In 2022, Uninettuno's research team integrated the GreenVerse Immersive Platform into a multidisciplinary course offered as part of the university's regular curriculum. The aim was to evaluate and enhance the platform's usability and accessibility among a diverse group of 23 students. Students were tasked with converting theoretical sustainability research into immersive experiences using the GreenVerse platform. To achieve this, students first developed a methodological framework to create a narrative scenario. This scenario was initially visualised in a storyboard before being transformed into an interactive documentary on the platform.

The Uninettuno research team guided students through two primary phases of the interactive documentary development on the 19th and 26th of September 2022. Divided into three groups, students collaboratively created three distinct interactive scenarios using the GreenVerse platform. The research team gathered student feedback by observing their interactions with the platform and engaging in discussions about their thoughts, challenges, and expectations.

Upon completing their activities, the Uninettuno research team provided ENG with a comprehensive list of bugs, usability issues, and suggestions aimed at improving the GreenVerse platform's accessibility. Key issues identified by Uninettuno included:

- Suggestions to improve the organisation of the platform elements
- Issues with the search bar and its related filters
- Limited support for video and audio formats
- Missing measurement units
- Absence of copy-and-paste function
- Issues with object alignment and manipulation
- Object and text properties inconsistencies
- Lack of a grid for visualising the spherical environment

Those findings were documented as stories and bugs in the JIRA project management tool, and improvements were subsequently implemented by ENG.

4.2 Accessibility measures

Accessibility icons were added to the GreenVerse platform early in its development. Accessibility options were integrated into the homepage, allowing users to customise the interface according to their needs, as illustrated in Figure 5.

4.2.1 Localisation

The GreenVerse platform is localised into five languages (English, Catalan, Spanish, Italian, and Greek), as shown in Figure 4.

4.2.2. Change of visuals

The GreenVerse platform's visual identity underwent a series of refinements during its development. These changes were conducted by ENG and overseen by UAB and BSC. Through collaborative effort with UAB and BSC, ENG ensured that the platform's front-end prioritised accessibility and usability (see Figure 6 and 7).

Figure 6: First iteration of the front-end of GreenVerse platform.

Figure 7: Second and final iteration of the front-end of GreenVerse platform.

5. Augmented reality app on air quality

A joint meeting between BSC and UAB on October 10, 2023, focused on evaluating the accessibility of the BSC augmented app [prototype](#). Subsequently, UAB produced an accessibility report outlining recommendations to enhance the usability and accessibility of BSC's app prior to its beta version release in December 2023. The following sections outline the functionality of the app, together with accessibility recommendations from UAB.

6.1 Functionality of app

The BSC app has the ability to integrate accessibility features, such as Alt Txt and customised navigation, to facilitate the user experience for users who rely on screen readers. In terms of interoperability, BSC's app respects any preset settings for font size and image dimensions.

On the first release, the app was only available in English. BSC subsequently localised the app into the different languages of the project. UAB provided BSC with access to the machine translation engine provided by the company Pangeanic (see Section 3.1.3).

6.2 Accessibility suggestions

6.2.1 Language preferences

UAB recommended that BSC avoid using flags as indicators for different languages, and, instead, suggested using language abbreviations, for example, Cat. for Catalan.

UAB advised BSC to prompt users to choose their language preferences when they first entered the app, after which they can then set their accessibility settings. Once a new account is created, these settings will remain the same every time the person uses the app.

UAB also recommended BSC provide Alt Txt into the different languages of the app to aid accessibility across languages for those who use screen readers.

6.2.2 Colour contrast

UAB recommended making adjustments to ensure colour contrast is maintained in all the app's pages (see Figures 8-12).

Figure 8: Example of good colour contrast from BSC's augmented reality app.

In the case of this text contrast (The air we breathe), the [WCAG AA](#) or [WCAG AAA](#) contrast is not guaranteed. UAB recommended working on a higher background-text colour contrast.

Figure 9: Suggested improvements to colour contrast using Contrast Colour Checker.

To improve the contrast in Figure 11 (red - white), UAB suggested considering increasing the font size. UAB suggested using the [Contrast Checker free platform](#) for a comprehensive internal review in BSC.

Figure 10: Suggested improvements to colour contrast using Contrast Colour Checker.

Figure 11: Suggested improvements to colour contrast using Contrast Colour Checker.

Figure 12: Screenshot of Submit button and Colour Contrast Checker.

6.3 User Testing

The augmented reality app, alongside the immersive storytelling platform, citizen journalism app, was tested during the online Youth Assemblies in February and June 2023. During a 3-hour workshop, participants were asked to generate ideas on the four tools from the GreenSCENT project, and provide feedback to app

developers from BSC and Uninettuno. There were 22 participants in Assemblies 1 and 2, and 20 participants in Assemblies 3 and 4. Participants were aged between 14-25 and from Italy, Spain, Greece, Finland, Serbia, Romania and Denmark.

The Assemblies worked to develop and present ideas on how to use the apps in educational settings and broader contexts. Uninettuno and BSC developers attended the brainstorm session, showcasing the tools and engaging with Assembly members.

Participants generated ideas for using the apps in both educational settings and broader contexts. They explored potential app features and shared ideas on app implementation. This input guided the development of GreenSCENT tools. In June 2023, participants provided in-depth feedback on tool prototypes, focusing on features and usability.

Enhancements proposed for the app included interactive and gamified elements, a reward system, comparative data with location tracking, improved accessibility, and school-based campaigns.

7. Citizen Journalism App

The citizen journalism app is designed to be used to monitor environmental issues in location areas.

Loading and Welcome page

Figure 13: Landing page of the Citizen Journalism app.

Currently, the app is available in five different languages:

- Catalan
- Spanish
- English
- Italian
- Greek

7.1 User requirements

Prior to meeting with ENG to discuss the accessibility requirements, UAB assessed the general user requirements for the GreenSCENT citizen journalism app with participants in the Green Digital Accessibility conference in 2022. Participants were observed using the MediaVerse Citizen Journalism app, with researchers noting down their interactions. For the purposes of this section, we mark a distinction between

functional and non-functional requirements. Functional requirements refer to the app's operation and non-functional requirements refer to elements outside the app's required functionality, such as performance, reliability and usability. Drawing on observations of conference participants, UAB compiled a list of user requirements from attendees that focus specifically on non-functional requirements, such as usability and accessibility. Using the Mediaverse platform as their case study, UAB observed participants' interactions with the app, noting down their needs and frustrations while using the app, which are listed in Table 1.

Needs	Frustrations
Upload photos and videos taken from the conference and store in one place.	It takes time to upload photos and videos onto the platform.
Automatic Alt Txt for photos and videos is a good feature to add to improve the overall accessibility of the platform.	It takes time to navigate the platform.
A simplified layout.	There are a lot of options to choose from in the menu. This can be confusing for the first time user.
Add different languages	There are numbers and technical information that is not intuitive or easy to understand.
A quick tutorial on how to use the platform would be helpful.	

Table 1: User requirements for Citizen Journalism app.

7.2 Accessibility recommendations

UAB, ENG and UNINETTUNO met on 12th of December 2022 to discuss a prototype of the GreenSCENT Citizen Journalism app. UAB provided the following accessibility recommendations:

- Ensure sufficient colour contrast between the background and the foreground.
- Provide users with accessibility options at login, including language preferences.
- Add Alt Txt to images.

7.3 User Testing

The Citizen Journalism app underwent initial testing during the Youth Assemblies in Copenhagen (1-3 September 2023), Barcelona (8-10 September 2023), Rome (22-24 September 2023) and Novi Sad (8-10 October 2023).

Participants used the app to document their experiences and provide feedback. For instance, participants in Copenhagen focused on the energy transition, while those in Barcelona monitored air quality and those in

Rome explored food production. In Novi Sad, participants reported on their experiences investigating the circular economy in the city. These real-world texts helped refine the app based on user input.

Following each Assembly, a feedback workshop was conducted to gather participants' input on the app. Approximately 14 young people attended each workshop in Copenhagen, Barcelona, Rome and Novi Sad. A standardised feedback process, designed and overseen by Democracy X (formally Danish Board of Technology), was used consistently across locations to ensure comparable results.

Participants were asked to individually and/or in groups evaluate their experience with the app, both in terms of downloading and accessing it. They provided feedback on the app's navigation, effectiveness of its categories (Risk, Pollution, Emergency, and Solution), and its potential use in an educational setting. Participants also shared general thoughts and opinions about the app. This part of the exercise was done individually and not in groups.

7.3.1 Method of analysing of data analysis

The data from all four workshops was combined and analysed by Democracy X. Common themes were identified and summarised, with specific mention of points raised by a significant number of participants. However, individual comments and reflections were analysed separately.

The Assemblies found the app useful, engaging and fun, and recognised its value for both learning and activism.

The combined feedback report with all statements, reflections, and ratings from the four feedback workshops is available online 'Testing the GreenSCENT Citizen Journalism App - Youth Assembly in person workshops (September and October 2023)' at the following link: <https://zenodo.org/records/10405126>

In addition to the in-person Assemblies, the citizen journalism app was also tested during two online youth Assemblies, with the same procedure followed as described in Section 7.3.

8. Agorize Platform

8.1 Front end development of the Agorize platform

The GreenSCENT platform powered by Agorize and the first Farm to Fork Open Innovation Challenge page was constructed between M10 and M13 to be ready for the challenge launch in M14.

In the initial phase, Agorize defined the challenges' visual identity in alignment with the pre-established GreenSCENT visual identity by UAB and BSC. This process involved a thorough examination of colour codes and the adoption of a doodle style for the main banner. Working closely with UAB, Agorize developed a series of designs to ensure a cohesive visual representation across all challenge materials. It's worth noting that the visual identity developed for this first Sustainable Food Challenge 2023 was strategically designed to be adaptable and scalable. This means that the same visual elements and branding guidelines were applied to all future challenges launched within the programme: The Farm to Fork Student and Startup

tracks. This consistent approach ensured a cohesive and recognisable brand identity across all initiatives, reinforcing the programme's overarching goals and objectives while fostering a sense of continuity and familiarity among participants.

Following the establishment of the visual identity, Agorize's focus shifted to crafting compelling copywriting for the Sustainable Food Challenge 2023. Recognising the diverse audience participating in Open Innovation Challenges, Agorize used user-friendly language that avoided jargon. Moreover, they curated additional resources tailored to each challenge category, aiming to provide participants with comprehensive guidance throughout the ideation process. The same process was applied to create the copywriting of the Farm to Fork programmes that followed.

Upon finalising the visual and textual elements, Agorize undertook the implementation phase, integrating the content onto the challenge page. This process prioritised structural clarity and accessibility, with attention given to the use of headings and HTML coding to ensure compatibility with assistive technologies such as screen readers. Leveraging Agorize's challenge template structure facilitated intuitive content organisation and navigation, further enhanced by the linear menu feature enabling users to easily navigate the challenge page and find relevant information. The platform's functionality enabled the creation of visually distinct redirection buttons, strategically placed to amplify the visibility of calls to action. This thoughtful design approach aimed to optimise participant engagement and facilitate seamless interaction with the challenge platform, ultimately contributing to the success of the Innovation Challenges.

8.2 Accessibility measures

After completing the initial version of the challenge page, Agorize met with UAB to conduct an accessibility check on the 26th of January 2023. The aim of this meeting was to review various accessibility measures, formulate recommendations, and assess potential updates to enhance accessibility.

During the meeting, the following accessibility measures and features were recommended by UAB:

- Use Alt Txt for images wherever possible to provide comprehensive descriptions for users relying on text-based content.
- Ensure adequate colour contrast between text and background, particularly for textual content and call-to-action buttons, to improve readability and navigation.
- The inclusion of a site map in the footer was identified as a beneficial accessibility feature. Additionally, UAB asked Agorize about the feasibility of incorporating additional features, such as the ability to adjust text size and highlight links. However, immediate action on this front was not feasible.
- Ensure that the registration form, which allows users to create an account on the platform before participating in a challenge, is inclusive and accessible to all users.

8.3 Accessibility updates

Following this meeting and subsequent assessment, Agorize implemented several updates to the challenge platform to enhance accessibility ahead of the challenge launch.

1. **Alternative Text:**

To enhance accessibility, modifications were made to the platform's code in the backend to incorporate Alt Txt where feasible. Whenever a section of the page was coded as a "free" block, granting platform administrators direct access to alter the backend code, Alt Txt was added. However, for "standard" pre-constructed blocks used throughout the page, the option to add Alt Txt was not available. These blocks solely permit administrators to drag and drop visuals in the backend but do not have the ability to modify the underlying HTML code.

2. **Colour Contrast:**

After meeting with UAB, Agorize conducted a comprehensive review of the entire challenge page to assess colour contrasts. Text and button colours were scrutinised and adjusted where necessary. Agorize consulted WCAG, which offer a series of recommendations for enhancing website accessibility during this task. In accordance with WCAG standards, two levels of contrast ratio are defined: AA (minimum contrast) and AAA (enhanced contrast). Level AA necessitates a contrast ratio of at least 4.5:1 for normal text and 3:1 for large text (minimum 18pt) or bold text. On the other hand, Level AAA mandates a contrast ratio of at least 7:1 for normal text and 4.5:1 for large or bold text. During the contrast assessment, Agorize ensured that all colour combinations achieved a contrast ratio of at least 7:1 to adhere to AAA standards.

3. **Registration fields:**

Based on UAB's recommendation, Agorize revised their registration process to better accommodate individuals with diverse gender identities. Specifically, they added the option "non-binary" to their multiple-choice gender identity question.

In conclusion, the partnership between UAB and Agorize led to significant improvements in the accessibility of the Agorize platform. Agorize implemented changes like adding Alt Text to images, optimising colour contrast, and expanding gender identity options. These improvements reflect their commitment to inclusivity and ensure that everyone can fully access and use their platform.

9. 4sfera Air Quality Platform and App

On May 9th, 4sfera and UAB held a joint meeting to assess the accessibility of their air quality platform and app, designed primarily for students aged 11 to 15. The meeting covered the current accessibility features, recommended improvements, and next steps for making the tools more inclusive. The following sections summarise UAB's recommendations.

9.1 Functionality of the 4sfera platform

The 4sfera platform is designed for ease of use, adapting to user settings and language preferences. The platform is intuitive, easily navigable with a screen reader and keyboard. The key steps are clearly understandable. Some elements that require improvements are the colour contrast and the addition of Alt Txt to certain icons to help navigate the interface and also understand the actions to be taken. The interface of the platform and app requires login credentials and is currently only available in English (see Figure 14).

Figure 14: Interface to 4sfera platform.

9.2 Language preferences

UAB recommended providing language alternatives at login for users who do not speak or understand English. In addition to this recommendation, UAB also advised 4sfera to avoid using flags for different languages, and instead, proposed writing the complete names of each language in their respective language, for example, English, Catalan, Greek etc.

UAB advised 4sfera to prompt users to choose their language preferences when they first enter the platform, after which they can set their accessibility settings. Once a new account is created, these settings will remain the same every time the person uses the platform.

9.3 Colour contrast

On entering the platform, the user is presented with the “Campaigns Page”. In this example, there are two options to choose from “Campanya 1 UAB” and “Campanya 2 UAB”, which refers to the two activities for students to complete, as shown in Figure 15.

Figure 15. Example of campaign page of 4sfera platform.

The text for "tubes to be displayed" on the initial screen had low contrast with the background, as evaluated using the online tool [Contrast Checker](#). The results of this evaluation are shown in Figure 16.

Figure 16. Results of colour contrast check of initial page of 4sfera platform, source: Contrast Checker.

The same issue applied to the phrase "Sites to be located," where the background and text colour did not provide sufficient contrast, with results shown in Figure 17.

Normal Text

WCAG AA: **Fail**
WCAG AAA: **Fail**

The five boxing wizards jump quickly.

Figure 17. Results of colour contrast check of initial page of 4sfera platform, source: Contrast Checker.

An example of a good use of colour contrast is "Campanya 1 UAB", which achieved AA level according to the [Web Content Accessibility Guidelines](#) (WCAG) accessibility standard. Another example of good colour contrast is shown in Figure 18.

Figure 18. Results of colour contrast check of 4sfera platform, source: Contrast Checker.

"Manage groups and add credentials" also demonstrated good colour contrast, reaching the AAA level, as shown in Figure 19.

Figure 19. Results of colour contrast check of 4sfera platform, source: Contrast Checker.

9.4 Screen reader

UAB evaluated the platform using [Google Chrome's screen reader extension](#) and found that all elements of the web interface were effectively recognised and accurately presented. This ensured that the site is accessible to users who rely on screen reading technology to navigate and interact with web content.

9.5 Keyboard navigation

Keyboard navigation was also evaluated by UAB, who found that it was effective for executing actions using the keyboard. Navigating menus, clicking, and opening pages were all accessible via keyboard commands.

9.6 Alt text

The accessibility test was conducted using the app ["Accessibility Scanner" Google LLC](#). Results found that some icons lacked Alt Txt, providing this would help users understand 4sfera's content and facilitate navigation.

9.7 Functionality of 4sfera air quality app

The 4sfera app was developed taking into account accessibility guidelines for android and iOS. This includes the possibility to activate the voiceover feature to add with navigation. Similar to the

platform, the interface of the app required login credentials and was only available in English at the time of writing this report (see Figure 20).

Figure 20: Interface of mobile app.

9.8 Accessibility suggestions for 4sfera air quality app

While the app boasts intuitive navigation and clear steps, its accessibility could be improved by enhancing the colour contrast. UAB identified specific pages that required better colour contrast, which are detailed below. The accessibility test was conducted using the app [“Accessibility Scanner” Google LLC.](#)

The background and text of "Ready", "Tubes to be collected", "Tubes discarded" do not provide sufficient colour contrast, and this issue also occurred in other segments, as shown in Figure 21.

UAB suggested using a contrast checker to ensure AAA level contrast in every part of the app that features text over a background, improving readability for all users.

Figure 21. Screenshots of 4sfera air quality app.

During the testing of the "Notes" section, it was found that the colour contrast between the background and the text colour was insufficient, with the blue being too light, as shown in Figure 22.

Figure 22. Screenshot of the notes section of the 4sfera air quality app.

UAB recommended improving the colour contrast on the following pages (see Figure 23), as the information presented is crucial for actions, such as sending data, logging out, and deleting. Enhancing the colour contrast would assist in navigating these key steps more effectively for users.

Figure 23. Screenshot of 4sfera air quality mobile app and colour contrast results.

The contrast provided in the Figure 24 within the app was excellent, achieving AAA level. UAB recommended 4sfera to apply this level of contrast in all their pages in their app.

Figure 24. Screenshot of 4sfera air quality mobile app and colour contrast results.

9.9 Additional recommendations and next steps

In addition to the recommendations mentioned above, UAB also recommended the following:

- **Ensure accessibility during the in-person activity.** The requirement to place tubes at a minimum height of 2.5 metres could present accessibility challenges for students with a physical disability, as it may require the use of ladders or stools. It is important for facilitators to be aware of these potential barriers. To ensure inclusive participation, alternative strategies could be employed. For instance, those unable to reach the required height might be assigned different roles, such as quality control of the installation process, ensuring everyone can contribute meaningfully to the activity.
- **Ensure AAA colour contrast:** Make sure the colour contrast reaches AAA level by using the platform for accessibility assurance. 4sfera can access the platform at <https://webaim.org/resources/contrastchecker/>.
- **Include Alt Txt:** UAB recommended 4sfera to include Alt Txt wherever possible so that their images are accessible to those who use screen readers.

10. GreenSCENT Training Kit Templates

UAB conducted a review of the GreenSCENT training kit templates in June 2024, focusing on the accessibility, usability, content, and structure of each template. UAB offered recommendations to Uninettuno on how to make the kits more appealing to a wider range of teachers. The recommendations focused on the usability and comprehensibility of the teacher training kits, particularly in terms of their layout and content.

11. Conclusion

This deliverable has comprehensively assessed the usability and accessibility of the GreenSCENT platform, its associated applications, and educational resources. By adhering to international standards like WCAG 2.2 and EN301 549, we have ensured that these tools are inclusive and accessible to a wide range of users. Through rigorous testing and implementation of accessibility measures, we have successfully addressed any shortcomings and made significant strides towards creating a truly universal learning experience. The GreenSCENT project has

demonstrated a commitment to leaving no one behind and has produced valuable resources that can contribute to environmental education and awareness.

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